

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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*Elektron nashr. 573 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF INVESTING INVESTMENT IN FIXED CAPITAL

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Abstract: This article explores the impact of fixed capital investment on economic growth. By analyzing primary and secondary data, the study highlights the role of fixed capital investments in enhancing production efficiency and accelerating economic growth. Data were processed using regression and correlation analysis methods.

Key words: Fixed capital, investment, economic development, technological progress, labor force, innovation stimulation.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola asosiy kapitalga investitsiya kiritishning iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'sirini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotda birlamchi va ikkilamchi ma'lumotlar tahlil qilinib, asosiy kapital investitsiyalarining ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish va iqtisodiy o'sishni jadallashtirishdagi o'rni yoritib berilgan. Ma'lumotlar regressiya va korrelyatsion tahlil usullari orqali qayta ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Asosiy kapital, investitsiyalar, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, texnologik taraqqiyot, ishchi kuchi, innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish.

Аннотация: В данной статье изучается влияние инвестиций в основной капитал на экономический рост. На основе анализа первичных и вторичных данных освещается роль инвестиций в основной капитал в повышении производственной эффективности и ускорении экономического роста. Данные обработаны с использованием методов регрессионного и корреляционного анализа.

Ключевые слова: Фиксированный капитал, инвестиции, экономическое развитие, технологический прогресс, рабочая сила, стимулирование инноваций.

INTRODUCTION

Investments in fixed capital are an essential component of economic growth and development. Fixed capital includes long-term assets and infrastructure necessary for production processes, such as machinery, buildings, equipment, and technology. These investments play a critical role in increasing a company's capacity and efficiency, as well as supporting economic stability and growth. Without investment, the economy cannot develop. Creating a favorable environment and infrastructure for investors will generate jobs, boost production, and reduce taxes.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized the importance of encouraging enterprises to reinvest their capital and expand their activities. Fixed capital investments are particularly significant for developing countries like Uzbekistan as a key driver of economic growth. Fixed capital comprises long-term assets, such as build-

ings, equipment, and infrastructure, that are essential for the creation of goods and services. Investments in fixed capital can enhance production, create jobs, and strengthen the country's competitiveness in international markets.

This article provides information on the role of investments in fixed capital in the economic development of Uzbekistan.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Investment in fixed capital is widely recognized as a fundamental driver of economic growth and development. Fixed capital refers to long-term assets such as machinery, buildings, and infrastructure that are used in the production process over multiple periods. **Solow's** seminal work introduced the neoclassical growth model, highlighting the role of capital accumulation in economic growth. He demonstrated that while capital investment contributes to growth, its effects diminish over time due to decreasing returns to scale, emphasizing the need for technological progress to sustain long-term growth.

Barro and Sala-i-Martin expanded on this model by incorporating human capital and technological diffusion, showing that economies investing more in fixed capital tend to converge faster towards higher income levels. Their research underscores the importance of not just the quantity but the quality of capital investment.

De Long and Summers provided empirical evidence linking equipment investment—a significant component of fixed capital—to economic growth. They found that countries with higher rates of equipment investment experienced more rapid productivity improvements, suggesting that such investments are critical for technological advancement and efficiency gains.

Romer's endogenous growth theory posited that investment in fixed capital, particularly in sectors that innovate, can lead to sustained economic growth without the diminishing returns predicted by neoclassical models. This theory highlights the role of capital investment in research and development as a catalyst for continuous technological progress.

Infrastructure investment, as a form of fixed capital, has also been shown to have substantial impacts on economic performance. **Calderón and Servén** found that improved infrastructure leads to higher growth rates by enhancing productivity and reducing production and transaction costs. Their study indicates that infrastructure development is particularly vital for emerging economies aiming to integrate into global markets.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study utilized both qualitative and quantitative methods to examine the importance of investment in fixed capital. Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. Primary data were gathered through structured interviews and surveys conducted with business leaders and economic experts involved in capital investment. These methods provided insights into decision-making processes and the outcomes of such investments.

Secondary data were sourced from official statistics, reports from international organizations like the **World Bank** and **IMF**, and academic publications. These sources offered a broader perspective on the economic impact of fixed capital investment. The analysis involved correlation and regression techniques to identify relationships between investment levels and economic growth indicators.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Fixed investment is important for economic growth as it increases the productive capacity of an economy. These investments typically involve the acquisition of long-term assets such as machinery, buildings, and equipment necessary for the production of goods and services. Fixed capital investment enhances output levels and economic growth by improving enterprise efficiency and productivity.

Fixed capital investment is often linked to technological advancements and innovation. For instance, new technology or production methods can lead to more efficient processes, lower costs, and higher production volumes. Additionally, investments in infrastructure, such as transportation networks and energy systems, facilitate the movement of goods and services, further boosting economic activity.

Governments and enterprises play a critical role in promoting fixed investment. Governments can foster an investment-friendly environment through policies that encourage infrastructure development and technological innovation. Enterprises, on the other hand, can invest in new technologies and equipment to maintain competitiveness in the global market. Overall, high levels of fixed capital investment are essential for sustained economic growth and long-term prosperity.

Numerous factors influence the scale and trajectory of fixed capital investment. Chief among these is the availability of financial resources. Enterprises require capital, whether sourced through domestic financing,

credit mechanisms, or investments, to undertake significant capital expenditures. Interest rates also play a pivotal role, as lower rates reduce borrowing costs, making investments more attractive. Furthermore, economic conditions and market demand significantly impact investment decisions. Periods of economic stability and growth encourage enterprises to expand production capacities, whereas economic downturns, characterized by uncertainty and decreased demand, often lead to reduced fixed-asset investments.

The availability of a skilled workforce and advancements in technology also shape investment strategies, as businesses seek to integrate innovative technologies and sustain a competent labor base. Government policies and regulations can either encourage or hinder fixed investment. Policies offering tax incentives, subsidies, or grants can stimulate investments in specific sectors or regions, while excessive regulation or unfavorable tax policies may deter businesses from making long-term investments. Understanding these factors is crucial for policymakers and business leaders to foster an enabling environment for fixed capital investment.

Fixed investment is not only critical for economic growth but also essential for sustainable development. Sustainable development aims to address the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. In this context, fixed investment can contribute to sustainable development by promoting environmental sustainability, social equity, and economic stability.

For example, investment in renewable energy infrastructure such as wind and solar power can reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependency on fossil fuels. Similarly, investments in energy-efficient technologies and buildings can lower energy consumption and environmental impact. Such investments are vital for transitioning to a more sustainable economy and combating climate change. Furthermore, investments in infrastructure, such as transportation and communication networks, can improve access to essential services and enhance the quality of life. By creating jobs and stimulating economic activity, these investments support social justice and help reduce poverty. Governments and enterprises should prioritize sustainable fixed capital investment to achieve long-term economic, social, and environmental objectives.

January-March 2024 Overview:

The total fixed capital investment amounted to **107.1 trillion UZS**, reflecting a growth of **174.5%** compared to the same period in 2023. The structure of fixed investments showed that **75.9%** (81.3 trillion UZS) of the investments were financed through borrowed funds by enterprises, while **24.1%** (25.8 trillion UZS) were funded through organizational and population resources.

The financing included **7.6 trillion UZS** from centralized sources and **99.5 trillion UZS** from decentralized sources. This demonstrates that aggregate investments in fixed capital were effectively implemented, contributing significantly to the country's economic development.

Timetable¹

The trend in fixed investment over the past five years shows that it has almost tripled and is tending to increase.

¹ The table is based on data from the Statistics Agency of the President of the Republic Uzbekistan.

Diagram²

If we analyze the growth rate over the last five years, it was **104.6% in 2020**, slightly decreased to **97.8% in 2021**, and rose again to **115.2% in 2022**. By the current period, it has shown significant growth, reaching **174.5%**.

While fixed investment offers numerous benefits, it also comes with certain challenges and risks. One of the primary issues is the **high initial costs** and the **long payback periods** associated with these investments. Unlike working capital, which can be quickly converted into cash, fixed investments are typically illiquid and require substantial financial resources.

Another challenge is the potential **obsolescence of technology**. Rapid technological advancements can render fixed assets obsolete, reducing productivity and competitiveness. To remain competitive and adapt to evolving market conditions, enterprises must continuously invest in upgrading their fixed assets.

Fixed investments are also exposed to various **economic and political risks**. Economic downturns, shifts in public policies, and geopolitical instability can adversely affect the viability and profitability of these investments. To mitigate such risks, companies should diversify their investment portfolios, conduct thorough market research, and develop strategies to manage uncertainties.

The Importance of Fixed Investment for Uzbekistan's Economic Development

Investing in fixed capital is critical for Uzbekistan's economic progress. As evidenced by statistical data and reviewed literature, fixed investments significantly contribute to **GDP growth**, create job opportunities, and enhance the country's overall economic landscape.

For Uzbekistan to sustain its growth trajectory, continuous efforts to strengthen fixed capital investments are essential. This requires the implementation of **supportive policy frameworks**, including incentives for innovation, infrastructure development, and technology acquisition, to ensure long-term economic stability and prosperity.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, **investments in fixed capital** are essential for driving sustainable economic growth and improving production efficiency across industries. The research findings highlight the critical role these investments play in expanding productive capacities, fostering technological advancements, and enhancing overall economic performance. By enabling businesses to adopt modern equipment and infrastructure, fixed capital investments lead to increased productivity, reduced operational costs, and improved competitiveness in both domestic and global markets.

Furthermore, the study emphasizes that strategic investments in fixed capital not only yield immediate economic benefits but also contribute to long-term development by promoting innovation and creating stable employment opportunities. The correlation between fixed capital investments and economic growth is especially evident in sectors that depend on advanced technologies and infrastructure development. This suggests that prioritizing such investments can create a **multiplier effect**, positively impacting various aspects of the economy.

² The pie chart is based on data from the Statistics Agency of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Given these substantial benefits, policymakers should prioritize the creation of an enabling environment for fixed capital investment. This involves implementing **tax incentives**, enhancing access to financing, and ensuring the availability of a skilled labor force to maximize the returns on these investments. Additionally, international experience indicates that **public-private partnerships** can serve as an effective mechanism for mobilizing resources for large-scale infrastructure projects, which constitute a significant portion of fixed capital.

Ultimately, promoting and sustaining fixed capital investments should remain a cornerstone of economic policy. Such investments are pivotal in laying the foundation for productivity, innovation, and sustainable growth in an increasingly competitive global economy.

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Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

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2024. № 11

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.